

Airborne Research and Survey Facility Data

CEDA summer work
placement

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- ARSF overview
- Sorting and summarising ARSF metadata held in legacy formats
- MOLES review
- Preparation of metadata for FAtCat
- Unix scripts -
 - Retrieve old data from Atlas
 - Write scripts to transfer to ingest directory
 - Generate header files, format data, preview images and information files ready for archive
 - Use deposit script to transfer to archive
- Move to FAtCat

NERCARSF Dornier aircraft

<http://arsf.nerc.ac.uk/images/g-envr.jpg>

ARSF Metadata

Began by cross-checking operations reports against NEODC archive and atom editor:

DETAILS OF AREAS SURVEYED

1986 SURVEY

Phase ..2...

Area No. and Name:	BROOMS BARN	Map Sheet Nos. O/S:	143/155
	86/1		
Flying Height:	3500 M	Direction Flown:	N/S
Flight Conditions:	POOR VIS	No. of Lines:	3
No. of 9" x 9" photo prints:	11	No. of Scan Lines:	5080
Film Forward Overlap (%):	30	No. of CCTs:	3
Ground Speed (knots):	165	Scan Speed rps:	12.5
Time Flown (GMT):	1112-1125	Tape Footage:	274
Research Team Availability:	INA	"S" Bend Correction:	YES

Aircraft: N.E.R.C. Navajo Chieftain G-BBXX

Camera: Wild RC8. wide angle 6" 15 Vag 396 lens

Scanner: Daedalus AADS 1268 11 channel Thematic Scanner with AADS 1840 film converter unit and Sabre III tape recorder

	00README	
	86_01	<i>Brooms Barn</i>
	86_02	<i>Blakey Ridge, Glaisdale Rigg</i>
	86_03	<i>Oxford Flood Plain</i>
	86_04	<i>Feltwell</i>
	86_06	<i>Rhondda</i>
	86_09	<i>Southover Heath, Swanley</i>
	86_10	<i>Leverton Marsh</i>
	86_11	<i>Morton Fen</i>
	86_12	<i>Skipwith Common</i>
	86_14	<i>Ripon</i>

Results: 2 records found

Edit	ProviderID	Created	Updated	Type	Title	Subtype	Status	Deployments
Edit	neodc.nerc.ac.uk	2007-10-02	2012-07-05 10:36	Activity	ARSF - Flight 86/01: Brooms Barn area	Activity Data Campaign	published	-
Edit	neodc.nerc.ac.uk	2007-10-02	2012-07-20 09:53	Activity	Data from the Photographic Camera on-board the Piper PA31 Navajo Chieftain G-NERC Aircraft during Flight 86/01 over the Brooms Barn Area	Deployment	published	-

Metadata Objects for Linking Environmental Sciences

- ARSF MOLES v.2 structure at its most basic:

- Approximately 1400 valid activities and deployments
- Also edited entire set of NEODC data entities in-line with the BADC metadata quality report (understandable title, explained acronyms, suitable summary etc.).

Further MOLES info: <http://team.ceda.ac.uk/trac/ceda/wiki/DatasetList>

Metadata Quality Report

Deployment Example

Data from the Photographic Camera on-board the Piper PA31 Navajo Chieftain G-NERC Aircraft during Flight 86/01 over the Brooms Barn Area

General Info

Title: Data from the Photographic Camera on-board the Piper PA31 Navajo Chieftain G-NERC Aircraft during Flight 86/01 over the Brooms Barn Area
Type: Activity
Sub-Type: Deployment
Publication State: published
URI: http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/neodc.nerc.ac.uk__ATOM__dep_11913659174823782

Author

Name

neodc.nerc.ac.uk

email

Online References

Relation	Title
Download	Download data from ARSF archive

Associated Data

Type	Title
Data Production Tool	ARSF WILD-RC8 Analogue Photographic camera
Observation Station	Piper PA31 Navajo Chieftain G-NERC Aircraft
Activity	ARSF - Flight 86/01: Brooms Barn area

Parent Activity

No data specified at present

Sub-Activities

None

Data Coverage

Spatial coverage			Temporal coverage	
Min X: 0.6	Max Y: 52.27	Max X 0.63	Start Date:	1986-07-16
	Min Y 52.27		End Date:	1986-07-16
Spatial resolution			Vertical extent	
No spatial resolution information available.			No vertical extent information available.	

http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/neodc.nerc.ac.uk__ATOM__dep_11913659174823782

How Can This Help?

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	
- = not applicable	n = no	y = yes	In Excel refers to file 'ARSF original Excel.xlsx		In Access refers to file 'Access archive.accdb'				
Activity/flight	In Operations Report	Has associated tapes	In archive	In atom editor	Has deployment	Spatial coverage added to deployment	Content added to deployment	Science Project info	Extra info
ARSF 85/RE River Estuaries	n	n	y	y	y	y	n		
1986									
ARSF 86/01 Brooms Barn	y	y	y	y	y	y	n		
ARSF 86/02 Blakey Ridge and Glaisdale Rigg	y	y	y	y	y	y	n		
ARSF 86/03 Oxford Flood Plain	y	y	y	y	y	y	n		
ARSF 86/04 Feltwell	y	y	y	y	y	n	n		no info on DT
ARSF 86/06 Rhondda	y	y	y	y	y	y	n		
ARSF 86/09 Southover Heath and Swanley	y	y	y	y	y	y	n		
ARSF 86/10 Leverton Marsh	y	y	y	y	y	y	n		
ARSF 86/11 Morton Fen	y	y	y	y	y	y	n		
ARSF 86/12 Skipwith Common	y	n	y	y	y	n	n		
ARSF 86/14 Ripon	y	y	y	y	y	y	n		
ARSF 86/15 Derwent Fells	y	y	n	y	y	y	n		
ARSF 86/16 Tay Estuary	y	y	n	y	y	y	n		
ARSF 86/17 Esthwaite Water	y	y	y	y	y	y	n		
ARSF 86/18 Dinnet	y	y	y	y	y	y	n		

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
1	path	archive	DATE	"AREA"	COUNTRY	LAT	LONG	TAPE	"ORBIT"		"SENSOR"
2	/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A11991	-	1986-06-11	PLYMOUTH	ENGLAND			A11991	1 21		ATM-86
3	/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A11992	-	1986-06-11	PLYMOUTH	ENGLAND			A11992	1 21		ATM-86
4	/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12264	-	1986-09-04	ROTHAMSTED	ENGLAND	51.8	-0.37	A12264	9/48		ATM-86
5	/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12180	/neodc/arsf/1986/86_01	1986-07-15	BROOMS BARN	ENGLAND	52.27	0.6	A12180	7/1		ATM-86
6	/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12181	/neodc/arsf/1986/86_01	1986-07-15	BROOMS BARN	ENGLAND	52.27	0.6	A12181	7/1		ATM-86
7	/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12182	/neodc/arsf/1986/86_01	1986-07-15	BROOMS BARN	ENGLAND	52.27	0.63	A12182	7/1		ATM-86
8	/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12112	/neodc/arsf/1986/86_02	1986-05-23	BLAKEY RIDGE	ENGLAND			A12112	5/2 (1)		ATM-86
9	/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12113	/neodc/arsf/1986/86_02	1986-05-23	BLAKEY RIDGE	ENGLAND	54.37	-0.97	A12113	5/2 (1)		ATM-86
10	/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12114	/neodc/arsf/1986/86_02	1986-05-23	BLAKEY RIDGE	ENGLAND	54.32	-0.95	A12114	5/2 (1)		ATM-86
11	/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12115	/neodc/arsf/1986/86_02	1986-05-23	BLAKEY RIDGE	ENGLAND	54.37	-0.95	A12115	5/2 (1)		ATM-86
12	/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12116	/neodc/arsf/1986/86_02	1986-05-23	BLAKEY RIDGE	ENGLAND	54.33	-0.93	A12116	5/2 (1)		ATM-86
13	/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12117	/neodc/arsf/1986/86_02	1986-05-23	BLAKEY RIDGE	ENGLAND	54.37	-0.93	A12117	5/2 (1)		ATM-86
14	/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12221	/neodc/arsf/1986/86_02	1986-07-22	BLAKEY RIDGE	ENGLAND	54.42	-0.85	A12221	7/2 (1)		ATM-86
15	/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12222	/neodc/arsf/1986/86_02	1986-07-22	BLAKEY RIDGE	ENGLAND	54.42	-0.83	A12222	7/2 (1)		ATM-86
16	/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12223	/neodc/arsf/1986/86_02	1986-07-22	BLAKEY RIDGE	ENGLAND	54.42	-0.82	A12223	7/2 (1)		ATM-86

Format of Data

- Computer compatible tapes held in Atlas tape store
- Unprocessed, no metadata, – raw
- A case of informed guesswork and ‘data archaeology’

Image Generation

```
LAYOUT BIL
NBITS 8
NBANDS 12
NROWS 1599
NCOLS 750
SKIPBYTES 564
```


Set Multispectral File Format Specifications for:

A12180_1.bil

Size Specifications:

Number of Lines	1599	File Header Bytes	564
Number of Columns	750	File Trailer Bytes	0
Number of Channels	12	Preline Bytes	0
Start Line Number	1	Postline Bytes	0
Start Column Number	1	Prechannel Bytes	0
		Postchannel Bytes	0

Band Interleave Format: BIL-Band Interleave by Line

Data Value Type: 8-bit Unsigned integer Swap Bytes

Treat Lines from Bottom to Top

Cancel OK

Image Generation

Pre-1984 problem:

1983

Can only be displayed in 1 band,
but still accurate

1982

Data format *very* unclear
– displays distorted
image split into different
bands

Script Development

```

Line
1 #!/bin/bash
2
3 #*1 = file to read paths from, *2 = place to copy to
4 specDir=*2
5
6 for line in `cat $1`
7 do
8
9     disk=`echo $line | tr '=' '\t' | awk '{ print $1 }'`
10    archive=`echo $line | tr '=' '\t' | awk '{ print $2 }'`
11    tapenum=`echo $line | tr '=' '\t' | awk '{ print $1 }' | tr '/' '\t' | awk '{ print $NF }'`
12    echo "The tape number is $tapenum"
13
14    if [ -d $archive ]
15    then
16        code=`echo $archive | tr "/" "\t" | awk '{ print $NF }'`
17        year=`echo $1 | sed 's/\.txt//g'`
18
19        newDir=`echo $specDir"/"$year"/"$code"/ATM`
20        mkdir -p $newDir
21        echo "Directory exists ($archive)"
22        echo "Creating directory ($newDir)"
23
24        for tape in `ls $disk`
25        do
26
27            size=`ls -l $disk/"$tape | awk '{ print $5 }'`
28            num=`echo $tape | tr '.' '\t' | awk '{ print $2 }'`
29            tp=`echo $tape | tr '.' '\t' | awk '{ print $1 }'`
30            tape2=`echo $tp_"$num`
31
32            if [ "$size" != 0 -a "$tape" != "tape.stderr" ]
33            then
34
35                L10dir=`echo $newDir"/L10`
36                rawdir=`echo $newDir"/raw/"$tapenum`
37                mkdir -p $L10dir
38                mkdir -p $rawdir
39
40                hdr=`echo $tape2".hdr`
41                echo "Writing header file $hdr..."
42                hdrdir=`echo $L10dir"/"$hdr`
43                touch $hdrdir
44                echo "LAYOUT BIL" >> $hdrdir
45                echo "NBITS 8" >> $hdrdir
46                echo "NBANDS 12" >> $hdrdir
47                scanst=`head -c564 $disk/"$tape | grep 'COUNT - START' | tr '/' '\t' | awk '{ print $6 }'`
48                scanfi=`head -c564 $disk/"$tape | grep 'COUNT - FINISH' | tr '/' '\t' | awk '{ print $6 }'`

```

path	archive
/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12264	-
/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12180	/neodc/arsf/1986/86_01
/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12181	86/15

Separate the two paths

If project exists in archive, create new directory in ingest directory with the code taken from the txt file and new 'ATM' directory

Then go through each 'sub' tape in the tape directory

Make /L10 and /raw directories in /ATM

Script Development

```

23 for tape in `ls $disk`
24 do
25   size=`ls -l $disk/"$tape | awk '{ print $5 }'`
26   num=`echo $tape | tr '.' '\t' | awk '{ print $2 }'`
27   tp=`echo $tape | tr '.' '\t' | awk '{ print $1 }'`
28   tape2=`echo $tp_"$num`
29
30   if [ "$size" != 0 -a "$tape" != "tape.stderr" ]
31   then
32     L10dir=`echo $newDir"/L10`
33     rawdir=`echo $newDir"/raw/"$tapenum`
34     mkdir -p $L10dir
35     mkdir -p $rawdir
36
37     hdr=`echo $tape2".hdr`
38     echo "Writing header file $hdr..."
39     hdrdir=`echo $L10dir/"$hdr`
40     touch $hdrdir
41     echo "LAYOUT BIL" >> $hdrdir
42     echo "NBITS 8" >> $hdrdir
43     echo "NBANDS 12" >> $hdrdir
44     scanst=`head -c564 $disk/"$tape | grep 'COUNT - START' | tr '/' '\t' | awk '{ print $6 }'`
45     scanfi=`head -c564 $disk/"$tape | grep 'COUNT - FINISH' | tr '/' '\t' | awk '{ print $6 }'`
46     lines=`expr $scanfi - $scanst`
47     echo "NROWS $lines" >> $hdrdir
48     echo "NCOLS 750" >> $hdrdir
49     echo "SKIPBYTES 564" >> $hdrdir
50
51     echo "$tape size = $size"
52     echo "Copying file to $rawdir..."
53     cp $disk/"$tape $rawdir
54     echo "Copying file to $L10dir..."
55     echo "Swapping bytes..."
56     dd if=$disk/"$tape of=$L10dir/"$tape2".bil" conv=swab
57     tapebil=`echo $L10dir/"$tape2".bil`
58
59     echo "Generating preview image..."
60     gdal_translate -of PNG -b 5 -b 3 -b 2 -outsizes 40% 40% $tapebil $L10dir/"$tape2".png
61
62   else
63     echo "$tape size = $size (null file)"
64
65   fi
66 done
67
68 elif [ $archive != '-' ]
69

```

← Create header file in /L10 directory

← Copy original tapes into /raw directory

← Create .bil files from raw tapes and copy these into /L10

← Generate preview image in /L10

Script Development

```

180 fi
181
182 #newtar='echo $rawdir"/"$stapenum".tar.gz"'
183 usedir='echo $rawdir"/"$stapenum"+"'
184 echo "Creating zipped tape archive"
185 tardir='echo $rawdir | sed "s/$stapenum/g"'
186 newtar='echo $tardir"/"$stapenum".tar.gz"'
187 cmd='echo "tar cvfz $newtar --directory=$tardir $stapenum"'
188 echo "tar cmd = "$cmd
189 $cmd
190 #rm $rawdir"/"$stapenum.*[0-9]
191 rm -rf $rawdir
192
193 readme='echo "readme.txt"'
194 readdir='echo $L10dir"/"$readme'
195 touch $readdir
196 echo "Readme" > $readdir
197 echo "The .bil image file(s) is/are converted from original Computer Compatible Tapes (CCTs), found in ATM/raw directory.\n\n" >> $readdir
198 echo "The .hdr header file(s) can be used to assist image viewing in various programs and contain information on layout, number of bands, number of rows/columns and number of bytes to skip at the
beginning of the file - these 'SKIPBYTES' contain the original CCT file header, which cannot be read by image display programs. This number varies in data from 1982-83 and is 564 bytes from 1984 onwards. " >> $readdir
199 echo "The 'NROWS' value is calculated by the difference between the 'Frame count start' and 'Frame count finish' in the original CCT file header." >> $readdir
200 echo "An alternative method is to minus the CCT header bytes from the total file size and divide this value by 9000 (750 rows x 12 bands). This method generally gives a difference of +/- 1 byte from the automatically
calculated method, which appears trivial when displaying the image." >> $readdir
201 echo "Each .bil image should also be displayed with 23 line prefix bytes and 12 line suffix bytes as the columns before and after these respectively contain null information.\n\n" >> $readdir
202 echo "The .png image file(s) is/are unix generated preview(s) which use the command: gdal translate -of PNG -b 5 -b 3 -b 2 -outsize 40% 40% tape.bil tape.png. This reformats the image to a PNG file in the bands R:5
G:3 and B:2, which displays the closest approximation of true colour. The command also resizes the file to 40% - a more suitable preview image size." >> $readdir
203
204 echo "$stapenum done."
205
206 done
207
208 echo "Done."
209
210
211 exit
  
```

← Create .tar.gz tape archive in the /raw directory

← Create a readme file in each /L10 directory

New Archive...

/neodc/arsf/1986/86_01/ATM/...

- Specific fields in csv format ready for the FAtCat relational databases

- Issues –

- Spatial coverage not actually specific to each tape
- Supplementary spatial coverage from elsewhere not in master spreadsheet
- Dates already on deployments don't match master spreadsheet exactly

path	archive	DATE	AREA	COUNTRY	LAT	LONG
/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12264	-	1986-09-04	ROTHAMSTED	ENGLAND	51.8	-0.37
/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12180	/neodc/arsf/1986/86_01	1986-07-15	BROOMS BARN	ENGLAND	52.27	0.6
/disks/pennines1/neodc_loading/ADS/ATM-86/A12181	86/15	1986-07-15	BROOMS BARN	ENGLAND	52.27	0.6

```
echo $bilpath";"$hdrpath";"$pngpath";"$date";ATM;L10;"$size";"$location", "$country";"$long";"$lat
```

```
/neodc/arsf/1986/86_01/ATM/L10/A12180_1.bil;/neodc/arsf/1986/86_01/ATM/L10/A12180_1.hdr;/neodc/arsf/1986/86_01/ATM/L10/A12180_1.png;1986-07-15;ATM;L10;18360564;BROOMS BARN,ENGLAND;0.6;52.27
```

What's Left

- Create deployments for newly created activities
- 1982 and 1983 image generation and data ingestion
- Scan all operations reports into CEDA repository, then link each deployment to the relevant report
- Rename a lot of archive directories...

84_11	<i>New Forest</i>
84_12	<i>Coed-y-Brenim</i>
84_13	<i>Ballantrae</i>
01_40	<i>Black Ven</i>
01_41	<i>?</i>
01_42	<i>Netherlands</i>
03_17	<i>Abisko</i>
03_20	<i>Glass Sat Cal</i> <i>?</i>
03_28	<i>Bath</i>

Questions?